

Catechol dioxygenase activity of a mononuclear iron(III)-phenanthroline complex

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Abstract : A mononuclear iron(III) complex, $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{NO}_3$ (**1**) (phen = 1,10-phenanthroline) has been synthesized and characterized in crystalline phase, and employed as an efficient catalytic system towards 3,5-di-*tert*-butylcatechol (DTBC) as the model substrate for mimicking of catechol dioxygenase enzyme in oxygen saturated methanol medium. Upon stoichiometric addition of DTBC pretreated with two equivalents of triethylamine (Et_3N) to the Fe^{III} complex in oxygen saturated methanol medium, the reaction produced an *in situ* catecholate adduct, $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2(\text{DTBC})]^+$. The Fe^{III} -catecholate adduct reacts with dioxygen to afford intradiol cleavage products in quantitative yield and exhibits intradiol dioxygenase activity, which is also discerned from the decrease in absorbance of the electronic spectral bands around 507 nm and 697 nm. The superior semiquinone character in **1** correlates well with its high reactivity toward O_2 and this trends provide substantial evidence for the substrate activation mechanism proposed for the oxidative intradiol cleavage of catechols.

Keywords : Iron(III), phenanthroline, bio-mimicking study, catechol dioxygenase activity.

Introduction

In the active site of numerous metalloenzymes like biological oxidase actively involves molecular oxygen (O_2) to activate the kinetically inert O_2 and used to mediate and to control the multi-electron redox reactions. In view of the great importance of oxidation reactions in industrial and synthetic processes and of the ongoing search for new and efficient oxidation catalysts, it is of paramount interest to elucidate the basic functional principles that govern such metallic reactivity of natural enzymes¹⁻³. From both environmental and economic point of view, the search for effective catalytic oxidation processes that use clean, inexpensive terminal oxidants, such as molecular oxygen or hydrogen peroxide is highly desired⁴. The oxidative cleavage of catechol and other dihydroxy aromatics is a key step in the biodegradation of naturally occurring aromatic molecules and many aromatic environmental pollutants by soil bacteria^{5,6}. Catechol dioxygenases are a class of non-heme iron enzymes that catalyse the oxidative cleavage of catechols. They are divided into two subclasses : the intradiol dioxygenases, which utilize a non-heme iron(III) cofactor in catalyzing the cleavage of the carbon-carbon bond between the two catechol oxygens;

and the extradiol dioxygenases, which utilize a non-heme iron(II) cofactor in catalyzing the cleavage of the carbon-carbon bond adjacent to the catechol oxygens^{7,8}. The study of iron(III) complexes of ligands with phenolate oxygen and pyridine nitrogen donors⁹⁻¹¹ have provided valuable information to elucidate the structure-function correlation for the active site geometries of the catechol dioxygenase enzymes. With the aim to develop more active catalytic systems and to gain new insight in the enzymatic mechanism, we have synthesized, structurally characterized and explored the catechol dioxygenase activity of a non-heme mononuclear Fe^{III} -phenanthroline complex (**1**) towards 3,5-di-*tert*-butylcatechol (DTBC) as the model substrate.

Results and discussion

*Synthesis and structural features of $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{NO}_3$ (**1**) :*

The iron(III) complex was synthesized by adding 1,10-phenanthroline into FeCl_3 in 2 : 1 molar ratio in acetic acid-water medium (60-40 v/v) and 1 mole of CAN was added into the reaction solution. Red coloured crystalline complex (**1**) resulted in good yield. Here, ammonium ceric nitrate acts as an oxidizing agent and helps to keep the

iron ion in +3 oxidation state. Further, it supplies nitrate ions to stable the cationic metal complex unit. The complex is sufficiently stable in air and in presence of moisture. The compound is soluble in almost all solvents like methanol, ethanol, dichloromethane, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide.

X-Ray structural analysis reveals that crystal lattice of **1** consists of mononuclear $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{NO}_3$ unit (Fig. 1) with a distorted octahedron FeN_4Cl_2 chromophore. The coordination includes two chelated symmetrical bidentate blockers ligated by four N atoms in **1** along with

Fig. 1. An ORTEP of $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{NO}_3$ (**1**) with atom numbering scheme and 30% probability ellipsoids for all non-hydrogen atoms.

two coordinated Cl atoms in mutual *cis* orientation in **1**. The angle $97.36(4)^\circ$ between the two coordinated chlorine atoms around iron(III) centre as $\text{Cl}(2)\text{-Fe}(1)\text{-Cl}(2^*)$ indicates the cisoid representation of the structure. The

Fe-N/Cl bond distances range from $2.132(3)\text{-}2.2683(10)$ Å and the difference Δ between the longest and shortest Fe-N/Cl bonds amounts 0.1363 Å. Comparative values of Fe-N and Fe-Cl bond distances of $2.250(11)$ Å and $2.246(4)$ Å were respectively found for the ferrous complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2\text{Cl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$, indicating a high-spin (HS) state¹².

Spectrophotometric investigation for the formation of Fe^{III} -catechol adduct :

In order to investigate the catechol dioxygenase reactivity, initially we studied the efficiency of formation of Fe^{III} -catechol adduct by **1** with 3,5-di-*tert*-butylcatechol (3,5-DTBC) in oxygen saturated methanol at room temperature (25°C). For any catalytic oxidation reactions, formation of the metal complex-substrate adduct remain the most fundamental aspects for the conversion of substrate to product. Spectrophotometric wavelength scan and mass spectral study consolidates the *in situ* production of the Fe^{III} -catechol adduct. For this purpose, a catalytic amount of this complex (1×10^{-4} M) solution was treated with 1×10^{-4} M of 3,5-DTBC and the course of the reaction was followed by recording the UV-Vis spectra of the mixture at an interval of 5 min for 1 h. Upon adding DTBC to the iron(III) complex, there was a gradual decrease in intensity of the band due to the catechol at 284 nm¹³ and an initial new band was formed at ~ 408 nm (Fig. 2) indicating the rapid formation of 3,5-DTBQ in solution. Interestingly at the same time, an intense catecholate-to-iron(III) LMCT band ~ 734 nm¹⁴ with gradual increase in intensity (Fig. 2) and a Fe^{II} -semi-quinone band¹⁴ which gradually decrease in intensity ~ 515 nm (Fig. 2) is observed for **1**. Electron Spray Ionization

Fig. 2. Increase of quinone band at 408 nm (left) after addition of 100 equivalents of (3,5-DTBC) to a solution containing iron complex (**1**) (10^{-4} M) in methanol at 25°C . Right : Formation of Fe^{III} -catechol adduct with increase of absorbance at 734 nm.

(ESI) mass spectral analysis, further consolidates the formation of Fe^{III}-catecholate adduct, [Fe(phen)₂DTBC]⁺ (*m/z* 636.47) in MeOH solution. Thus, spectrophotometric wavelength scan and mass spectral study consolidates the *in situ* production of the Fe^{III}-catecholate adduct which is attributed to DTBC-to-iron(III) LMCT transitions involving two different catecholate ligand orbitals¹⁵; hence two bands ~515 nm and 734 nm are observed in favour of bidentate coordination of catechol to Fe^{III} centre. A similar observation of two catecholate-to-iron(III) LMCT bands has been made for the catecholate adducts of iron(III) complexes of tridentate 3N¹⁶, tetradentate 4N^{17,18} ligands.

Reactivity of in situ Fe^{III}-catecholate adduct toward dioxygen :

The reactivity of the *in situ* Fe^{III}-catecholate adduct toward dioxygen was investigated to determine the catechol cleavage products. The red solution of **1** reacts with dioxygen in methanol at 25 °C over a period of 6 h to give a green solution. During the reaction, the catecholate-to-iron(III) adduct is found to react as observed from the decrease in absorbance of the catecholate-to-iron(III) LMCT band at ~700 and 507 nm (Fig. 3). The disappearance of the charge-transfer bands (Fig. 3) indicates the oxidation of bound catecholate. The disappearance of the lower-energy catecholate-to-iron(III) LMCT band at ~700 nm on oxygenation exhibits pseudo-first order kinetics, as judged from the linearity of the plot [1 + log (Absorbance)] versus time^{19,20} (Fig. 4) and the value of k_{obs}

[k_{obs} is the pseudo-first order rate constant] was obtained from the slope of the plot. The pseudo-first order rate constant was determined as $k_{\text{obs}} : 1.62 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$. The rate of disappearance of this LMCT band at ~700 nm for this Fe^{III}-catecholate adduct is slower than the rate disappearance of the lower energy catecholate-to-iron(III) LMCT for the complexes reported by Paine *et al.*, Que *et al.* and Palanadivar *et al.*^{15,21,22}. This result indicates that isolated Fe-catecholate complex reacts more effectively with dioxygen compared to *in situ* formed catecholate adducts. Further, the oxidized products from 3,5-di-*tert*-butylcatechol were identified by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. The distribution of catechol-derived products was found mainly 3,5-di-*tert*-butyl-1-oxacyclohepta-3,5-diene-2,7-dione, as intradiol cleavage product in quantitative yield along with the formation of little 3,5-di-*tert*-butylbenzoquinone.

Analyses of 3,5-di-tert-butyl catechol cleavage products :

Dioxygen was bubbled through the solution of *in situ* formed catecholate adduct and then allowed to stir for 6 h at RT under oxygen atmosphere. The red solution slowly turned to green. The residue was then treated with 10 mL of 3 M HCl, the organic products were extracted with diethylether (3 × 15 mL) and dried over magnesium sulfate. Removal of solvent gave the catechol cleavage products. The organic products were analyzed by ¹H NMR spectroscopy (Fig. 5). ¹H NMR data for 3,5-di-*tert*-butyl

Fig. 3. Progress of the reaction of the *in situ* formed Fe^{III}-catecholate adduct, [Fe(phen)₂(DTBC)]⁺ with O₂ in MeOH solution. The disappearance of the DBC²⁻-to-iron(III) charge transfer band is monitored.

Fig. 4. Plot of [1 + log (Absorbance)] versus time for the reaction of $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2(\text{DTBC})]^+$ with O_2 at 25 °C in MeOH solution.

situ catecholate adducts of the iron(III) complex is expected of six-coordinate geometry without any labile groups, which favours substrate-activation^{23,24} rather than dioxygen-activation²⁵⁻²⁸ pathway as the latter requires a vacant coordination site on the catecholate adduct for oxygen coordination followed by activation. From the literature it is revealed that the steric and electronic properties of ligands coordinated to iron(III) lead to a dramatic difference in the cleavage preferences between the structurally similar catalysts and that there are subtle factors yet to be identified that modulate the oxidative cleavage mechanism. Palaniandavar *et al.*²⁹ showed the exclusive production of extradiol products by mononuclear iron(III) complexes consisting 4N ligands while Ghosh *et al.*³⁰ cited

Fig. 5. ^1H NMR spectrum of 3,5-di-*tert*-butyl-1-oxacyclohepta-3,5-diene-2,7-dione [marked a and b are indicating the protons in aromatic ring].

catechol cleavage products (300 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : 3,5-di-*tert*-butyl-1-oxacyclohepta-3,5-diene-2,7-dione (D) : δ = 1.19 (9H, s), 1.22 (9H, s), 6.14 (1H, d), 6.96 (1H, d).

Mechanistic framework for catechol dioxygenase activity of the iron(III) complex (1) :

The formation of intradiol cleavage product for the *in*

intradiol catechol cleaved products as major products by iron(III) complexes. But, in our case, we also found intradiol products as major products during oxygenase activity. The ESI-MS data of the solution immediately after reacting the *in situ* formed Fe^{III} -catecholate adduct with O_2 provides fundamental information. The mass spectrum of the reaction mixture exhibits numerous characteristics peaks

Fig. 6. ESI mass spectrum of the reaction mixture of the *in situ* formed Fe^{III}-catecholate adduct, [Fe(phenh)(DTBC)]⁺ with O₂ in MeOH solution.

at m/z 243.09, 259.45, 635.46, 692.10 with isotope distribution patterns which corroborate respectively [Na(DTBO)]⁺, [Na(3,5-di-*tert*-butyl-1-oxacyclohepta-3,5-diene-2,7-dione)]⁺, [Fe(phen)₂(DTBC)H]⁺ and [Fe(phen)₂(DTBC)(O-OH)]⁺ species (Fig. 6). Also, simultaneously hydrogen peroxide was produced during the catechol dioxygenase activity by *in situ* formed catecholate adduct. From ESI mass spectrometric analysis and literature review it is revealed that at the primary stage 3,5-DTBC behaves as a bidentate chelator towards mononuclear Fe^{III} complex and turns into an octahedral Fe^{III}-catecholate adduct, which exhibits no preference for molecular oxygen activation. Later, formation of semiquinone-Fe^{II} species in solution facilitates substrate activation mechanism and provides one electron from Fe^{II} to the anti-bonding orbital of dioxygen generates oxo-species in solution. Further, the acyl group migration produces the intradiol cleavage products and hydrogen peroxide. Probably, the intradiol catechol cleavage reaction proceeded by an iron(III) peroxo intermediate that underwent 1,2-Criegee rearrangement to yield the intradiol catechol cleaved products analogous to the native enzyme. The catalytic cycle as follows.

Scheme 1. Proposed mechanism for intradiol cleavage pathway.

Experimental

Chemicals, solvents and starting materials :

High purity 3,5-di-*tert*-butylcatechol (DTBC) (Aldrich, USA), iron(III) chloride hexahydrate (Merck, India), 1,10-phenanthroline (Merck, India), ceric ammonium nitrate (Merck, India) and all other solvents were purchased from the respective concerns and used as received. All other chemicals and solvents were of analytical grade and were used as received without further purification.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–300 cm^{-1}) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR model RX1 spectrometer. Ground-state absorption was made with a Jasco model V-730 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC300 spectrometer. Electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectrum was recorded using a Q-tof-micro quadrupole mass spectrometer.

Synthesis of the iron(III) complex :

The iron(III) complex was previously prepared by our group and employed as an efficient catalytic system to different primary and secondary alcohols⁴. Mononuclear complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{NO}_3$ (**1**) was prepared from chloride salt of iron(III) using 1 : 2 : 1 mole ratio of the metal, 1,10-phenanthroline and ammonium ceric nitrate (CAN). Typical synthesis is described in the following : An acetic acid-water mixing (6 : 4) solution (5 mL) of phen (0.396 g, 2 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.270 g, 1 mmol) in the same solvent (10 mL) keeping the solution on magnetic stirrer with slow stirring (450 rpm). Then solid CAN (550 mg, 1 mmol) was added portionwise into the pink solution and stirring continued to 30 min more. The pink solution turned into red and the supernatant liquid was kept in air for slow evaporation. After 7–10 days the complex **1** was separated out and washed with hexane and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield (based on metal salt) 0.210 g (77.7%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_2\text{Fe}$ (**1**) : C, 52.48; H, 2.93; N, 12.75. Found : C, 52.53; H, 2.98; N, 12.83; IR (KBr pellet) : 1384 (s), 1426 (m), 1517(s) cm^{-1} .

Kinetics and reactivity studies :

Kinetic analysis of the catechol cleavage reactions were carried out by time-dependent measurement of the disap-

pearance of the lower energy DBC^{2-} -to-iron(III) LMCT band at ambient temperature (25 °C) by exposing to molecular oxygen. The methanol solvent was equilibrated at the atmospheric pressure of O_2 at 25 °C. The oxygen activation by metal complexes is a solvent dependent process and herein we performed the oxygen activation study in oxygen saturated methanol solvent.

Conclusions

The reported mononuclear iron(III) complex (**1**) of the phenanthroline ligand was synthesized and characterized in crystalline phase. Presence of two labile chloride ions in *cis*-position at the primary zone of coordination for iron centre helps the substrate molecule (DTBC) to form a substrate-enzyme adduct. The *in situ* Fe^{III} -catecholate species, $[\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2(\text{DTBC})]^+$ displays no vacant coordination site for coordination of dioxygen and effectively exhibits intradiol catechol dioxygenase activity in oxygen saturated methanol medium via substrate activation mechanistic pathways.

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